

Chemical Studies of *Convolvulus puricaulis*, Chois—I

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Convolvulus puricaulis Chois (family : Convolvulaceae, in Hindi : Shankhapushpi) which widely grows in Northern India has been reported in Ayurvedic system of medicine to possess hypotensive effect and this led us to undertake a systematic chemical examination of the whole plant. In the present communication the presence of scopoletin, D-glucose and maltose in 1% HCl soluble portion and β -sitosterol and ceryl alcohol in nonsaponified part has been reported.

EXPERIMENTAL

Freshly dried powdered plant (4.5 kg) collected in April and May on extraction with rectified spirit gave a syrupy liquid extractive (403 g.) which was treated with 1% HCl solution and stirred for 4 hrs. The soluble portion was extracted with chloroform which on solvent removal gave a syrupy mass (A) (3.2 g). The remaining 1% HCl solution was basified with ammonia and again extracted with CHCl_3 . This extract on CHCl_3 removal gave a syrupy mass (B) (0.8 g).

The syrupy mass (A) showed three spots on T.L.C. (over silica gel G, with CHCl_3 as developer and under U.V. light). Total mass was therefore run over a column of silica gel (60 g.), using chloroform as eluent which gave a yellow solid. This on crystallisation with ethylacetate gave a needle shaped crystalline compound (0.33 g) m.p. 204° , C, 62.19%, H, 4.6%, M^+ 192 consistent with the molecular formula $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_8\text{O}_4$. The U.V. and I.R. spectra of the compound were characteristic of 6-methoxy-7-hydroxy coumarin (scopoletin). N.M.R. spectrum showed [$-\text{O}-\text{CH}_3$, 3.8 δ , three proton singlet; two pairs of doublets, (a pair of AB quartet) centered at 6.1 δ and 7.7 δ corresponding to C_3-H and C_4-H with $J = 9$ c.ps indicating these protons on adjacent carbon atoms of a double bond; two aromatic protons (singlets) C_8-H and C_5-H at 6.9 δ and 7.03 δ respectively; broad stretching at 8.88 indicative of a $-\text{OH}$ which showed one exchangeable proton with D_2O]. The identity was further established by the preparation of the acetate m.p. (reported $177-8^\circ$)¹.

Scopoletin was also isolated from the syrupy mass (B) by chromatography over alumina (25 g.). From the nonsaponifiable portion of the water insoluble fraction a flexy compound, m.p. $136-7^\circ$ (0.046%) responding to Liebermann Burchard test was obtained. It was identified as β -sitosterol from its benzoate derivative m.p. 143° (reported 145°)² and m.m.p. (Found : C, 84.07%, H, 11.61%. $\text{C}_{29}\text{H}_{50}\text{O}$ required, C, 84.06%, H, 12.02%).

1. S. H. Head Frank and Alexander Robertson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 1241.
2. I. Hilborn and H. M. Bunbury, Dictionary of Organic Compounds (Eyre and Spottiswoode, London, 1953).

The product obtained from middle fraction on repeated precipitation by methanol gave a waxy solid m.p. $77-8^{\circ}$ (1.1 g., 0.025%) which was found to be a straight chain alcohol, ceryl alcohol from its I.R. spectrum ($\frac{KBr}{max}$ 700, 720, 735, 2800, 2850 and 3350 cm^{-1}) and from its acetate derivative m.p. $62-5^{\circ}$ (reported 65°)². This gave m.m.p. of $77-8^{\circ}$ with authentic sample of ceryl alcohol. (Found : C, 81.47%, H, 13.44%. $C_{26}H_{54}O$ required, C, 81.67%, H, 14.13%).

Presence of D-glucose and maltose (Rf. 0.17 and 0.10 reported³, 0.18 and 0.11 respectively) has been confirmed by paper chromatography (descending, Whatman No. 1) using *n*-butanol, acetic acid and water (40 : 10 : 50) as irrigating solvent and aniline oxalate as developer.

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